

Hydrogen production from urea in human urine using segregated systems

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ABSTRACT

Removal of nitrogen compounds through biological processes represents the highest energy consumption in conventional centralised wastewater treatment facilities. Alternatively, segregated systems, where wastewater is treated at its source, present the potential to provide value to nitrogen-rich compounds contained in wastewater like urea. This paper demonstrates the feasibility of a novel process to recover energy from human urine based on the pre-isolation of urea to decrease the energy requirements for its thermal decomposition compared to the conventional thermal treatment when in solution, followed by its decomposition into hydrogen. Herein, urea is separated from an aqueous solution by adsorption onto activated carbon. Thermal urea desorption and decomposition into ammonia and CO₂ at 250 °C leads to full regeneration of the carbon, showing a constant adsorption capacity for at least 5 consecutive adsorption/desorption cycles. Finally, when the regeneration and urea decomposition step is coupled to an ammonia decomposition catalyst, hydrogen is produced to be used as an energy fuel. This process opens the door to a new way of circular economy by energy recovery from hydrogen-rich components in segregated wastewater streams. Preliminary energy balances show that the adoption of this energy recovery system in a city of 160,000 inhabitants would lead to a daily hydrogen production of 430 kg, with a net energy production of 2,500 kWh/day. In addition, such waste-to-energy process would lead to energy savings of 4,600 kWh/day in a conventional wastewater treatment plant reducing its energy consumption by around 35%.

1. Introduction

Access to energy and water are at the foundation of any economic and social development. The growing global population and the economic shift towards more resource-intensive models is stressing the availability of energy and fresh water (Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries, 2017; UNESCO, 2019). Guaranteeing global access to these two interrelated resources, energy and water, requires the development of new sustainable processes to decrease the energy consumption in the water cycle, especially in wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). Even more attractive is the possibility of recovering resources from wastewater streams in a circular economy approach.

Conventional sewage systems follow a centralised model. Wastewater is normally collected and transported in centralized sewer systems to be treated in large plants, where nitrogen compounds are removed biologically. It is estimated that nitrogen uptake through nitrification/denitrification processes requires an electrical demand of ~45 MJkg-N

⁻¹ in modern WWTPs (Maurer et al., 2003). WWTP commonly recover energy in the form of biogas through anaerobic digestion of the sludge, which can provide around 30% of energy demand in the plant (Palatsi et al., 2021; Stillwell et al., 2010).

In contrast, segregated systems are a promising new avenue that separates and treats wastewater streams directly at the source. At this stage, wastewater contains the highest concentration of targeted pollutants (Rossi et al., 2009). Additionally, the presence of other contaminants that can interfere in the treatment is minimal. This also enables the development of more efficient treatments and furthermore, the adoption of resource recovery strategies (Estévez et al., 2022; Tao et al., 2019). This approach differs from centralised WWTPs which are designed to unselectively remove several pollutants according to the local regulations.

In this regard, urine contributes to 80% of all the nitrogen produced in households, mainly in the form of urea ((NH₂)₂CO), in less than 1% of the total volume of domestic wastewater (Egle et al., 2015). An average

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human being produces approximately 500 L of urine annually (Von Münch and Winker, 2011), with an average urea concentration of 20,000 mg/L (Simha et al., 2018). Due to the high content of hydrogen in urea (6.7 wt.%), up to 0.4 kg of H₂ can be recovered per person yearly. Bio-hydrogen production is gaining increasingly attention to be used as a fuel with low carbon footprint (Baeyens et al., 2020; Li et al., 2020). Currently, urine source-separation is accomplished by utilizing urine-diversion toilets, which can be used to collect undiluted or low diluted urine (Rossi et al., 2009). These systems have been studied to recover nutrients N, P, K to be used as fertilisers (Tao et al., 2019; Zamora et al., 2017a, 2017b). However, few studies have explored the potential of energy recovery from urine in domestic wastewater, focusing mainly on the use of microbial fuel cells for ammonium recovery and hydrogen production (Kuntke et al., 2014, 2012).

Urea can be separated from solution using adsorption. Several adsorbent materials have been studied with particular attention to carbon-based materials (Ganesapillai et al., 2015; Kameda et al., 2020; Ooi et al., 2017), silica (Cheah et al., 2016), zeolites (Wernert et al., 2005) and chitosan and its derivatives (Wilson and Xue, 2013; Xue and Wilson, 2016). When heated up, urea decomposes into ammonia and isocyanic acid, the latter can then react with water to be hydrolysed into ammonia and carbon dioxide (Lundström et al., 2011). The thermal decomposition of urea has been studied and widely used to produce ammonia in exhausts of engines for the selective catalytic reduction of NO_x (Bernhard et al., 2012; Lundström et al., 2011). Finally, ammonia has attracted significant attention as a hydrogen storage molecule (Smith et al., 2020). Ammonia can be catalytically decomposed into H₂ and N₂ using metal-based catalysts, in which ruthenium has shown the highest catalytic activity (Bell et al., 2017; Hill and Torrente-Murciano, 2015; Hu et al., 2019b, 2019a). The resulting H₂ can be directly used to produce energy in fuel cells (Taner, 2018), although other uses as reagent for steel production (Li et al., 2021) or enriching the natural gas grid (Deng et al., 2022) are also being explored.

In this work, we present an innovative process of energy recovery from human urine. The process is based on the integration of three steps. First, urea is recovered from aqueous solution by adsorption onto

commercial activated carbon. Second, a thermal treatment is used to regenerate the adsorbent, leading to the simultaneous decomposition of urea into ammonia and carbon dioxide. And third, hydrogen is produced through the catalytic decomposition of ammonia to be used as a fuel. A scheme of the overall process is shown in Fig. 1. This new approach presents a more efficient removal of nitrogen compounds, targeting urea from urine, through initial isolation at its source, greatly reducing the energy requirements in comparison to conventional thermal treatments, overcoming the issue of the high specific heat capacity of water. As a result, this work promotes the circularity in the water cycle by transforming nitrogen-based hydrogen-rich pollutants into resources, contributing to the water-energy nexus. Additionally, this process reduces the energy consumption in WWTP significantly, and promotes the deployment of hydrogen as an energy vector.

2. Materials & methods

2.1. Adsorption experiments

Urea adsorption experiments were carried out in batch using 28 mL vials placed inside a heating block at a constant temperature of 30, 45 or 60 °C. Activated carbon (0.5 g, Vertex ROX 0.8) was added to 12.5 mL of an aqueous urea solution with different concentrations and the suspension was magnetically stirred for time enough to ensure equilibrium was reached (1 h). In the kinetic studies, the adsorption extension was evaluated at different times. Samples were collected and filtered (0.45 μm pore size), and the supernatant analysed to quantify urea concentration. A control experiment without activated carbon was carried out to analyse other urea removal pathways, observing that the change in urea concentration was negligible.

The amount of urea adsorbed was determined using Eq. (1).

$$q = \frac{(C_0 - C_f)V}{m} \quad (1)$$

where q (mg/g) is the amount of urea adsorbed normalized by the adsorbent mass (when equilibrium is reached, it is named as adsorption

Fig. 1. Scheme of the designed process for energy recovery from segregated wastewater.

capacity q_e , C_0 and C_f (mg/L) are the initial and the final concentration of urea in solution respectively, V (mL) is the volume of the solution and m (g) is the mass of adsorbent.

The concentration of urea in solution was determined using a colorimetric method. A colour reagent was prepared, consisting of 4% w/v p-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (99%, Sigma Aldrich) and 4% v/v concentrated sulphuric acid (98%, Fisher Scientific) dissolved in absolute ethanol (Fisher Scientific). The colour reagent (0.5 mL) was added to the urea problem solution (2 mL). The mixture was stabilized for 30 min and then the absorbance was measured in a spectrophotometer at 430 nm against a blank of colour reagent (0.5 mL) and water (2 mL). All the experiments were carried out in triplicate and the associated error is calculated as the standard deviation of the three experiments.

2.2. Thermal regeneration of activated carbon and decomposition of urea into ammonia

After adsorption, once equilibrium was reached, activated carbon was dried overnight at 80 °C under vacuum to remove the excess of water. This material is hereafter named as *saturated carbon*, though it has to be noted that once equilibrium is reached, not full saturation of the surface of the carbon is achieved. Temperature programmed desorption (TPD) analyses of fresh and saturated activated carbon (50 mg) were carried out using a Micromeritics Autochem II chemisorption analyser equipped with a MKS Cirrus 2 mass spectrometer. The studied temperature range was 50 - 300 °C, with a temperature increase rate of 10 °C/min under argon flow (50 mL/min). Mass to charge ratios (m/z) of 17, 43 and 44 and were analysed to monitor ammonia, isocyanic acid and carbon dioxide respectively in the outlet gas (Lundström et al., 2011). Carbon regeneration experiments were carried out by placing a bed of saturated carbon (4 - 10 g) in a stainless-steel reactor (16 mm inner diameter), held by glass wool and glass beads at the bottom and top of the bed. Nitrogen was flowed through the bed (20 mL/min) and the temperature was increased up to 250 °C with a temperature increase rate of 10 °C/min, measured with a thermocouple placed in the middle of the bed, and held for 210 min. Nitrogen was used instead of air to avoid the potential combustion of carbon or the released gases (e.g. ammonia). Adsorption experiments as described above were performed with the regenerated carbon to evaluate the adsorption capacity after each desorption cycle. Control experiments with the saturated carbons were done and no further adsorption was observed as expected.

2.3. Hydrogen production

An ammonia decomposition catalyst consisting of Ru (7% wt.) supported on carbon nanotubes was prepared by incipient wetness impregnation method using $\text{Ru}(\text{NO})(\text{NO}_3)_3$ (Alfa Aesar) as ruthenium precursor as previously reported (Hill and Torrente-Murciano, 2014). A bed of the dry saturated carbon (4.5 g) was placed in a stainless-steel reactor (10 mm inner diameter), held by steel and quartz wool at the bottom and top of the bed. The ammonia decomposition catalyst (60 mg) was placed in a second reactor (8 mm inner diameter) in series after the first one. The catalyst was placed in a bed dispersed with silicon carbide to ensure good mass and heat transfer (other cheaper inert materials such as olivine or cristobalite could also be used), held by quartz and steel wool at the bottom and the top. Pre-reduction of the catalyst was done by flowing H_2 through the catalytic bed at 250 °C and the activated carbon bed at room temperature. After that, the activated carbon temperature was raised to 200 °C and the catalytic bed to 400 °C under helium flow (4 mL/min). The concentration of ammonia and hydrogen in the outlet gas was measured using a gas chromatographer equipped with a thermo-conductivity detector.

3. Results and discussion

The process herein designed for energy recovery in the form of

hydrogen from urea present in human urine consists of 3 main steps. Firstly, urea is recovered from an aqueous solution by its adsorption onto commercial activated carbon. Secondly, a thermal treatment is used to regenerate the carbon adsorbent leading to the simultaneous decomposition of urea into ammonia and carbon dioxide. And thirdly, hydrogen is produced through the catalytic decomposition of ammonia to be used as an energy fuel.

In this work, we study the three steps of the process to demonstrate its feasibility and we carry out an energetic analysis to estimate the potential for the production of energy from the urea present in domestic wastewater.

3.1. Step 1. Adsorption of urea from domestic wastewater

The first step of the process consists of the recovery of urea from an aqueous solution via adsorption onto commercial activated carbon used as adsorbent. Activated carbon was selected after a preliminary screening of materials (Table S1, Supplementary Information). Activated carbon is a cheap and renewable material from biomass. It normally presents a very high surface area, and it is widely used to remove organic compounds from water. Additionally, activated carbon is easy to modify and functionalise, enabling the development of materials for the efficient removal of specific pollutants, based on their individual interactions (Saleem et al., 2019). Using adsorption, we minimise the energy requirements associated with thermal treatment of wastewater by the pre-isolation of urea, in contrast with industrial hydrolysers where urea is decomposed while in solution (Rahimpour, 2004). Equilibrium and kinetic experiments of adsorption of urea onto activated carbon were carried out to characterise the adsorption process and elucidate the adsorption mechanism in the selected commercial activated carbon.

The adsorption equilibrium of commercial activated carbon was determined using different initial concentrations of urea up to 60,000 mg/L at 30, 45 and 60 °C. The adsorption isotherms in Fig. 2 are obtained by plotting the amount of urea adsorbed (q_e) versus the concentration of urea in the solution (C_e) under equilibrium conditions.

Adsorption capacity is higher at lower temperatures, showing that adsorption is favoured at low temperatures and is hence exothermic as expected in adsorption processes (Worch, 2012). The adsorption capacities shown in these equilibrium experiments and the large linear region of the isotherms in Fig. 2 suggest a relatively low affinity of urea for the activated carbon. This observation is related to the similarity of urea and water molecules, both being small, polar and neutral compounds. In addition, urea can form hydrogen bonds and therefore has a high affinity to water, making difficult its separation (Lehmann et al., 1981).

Significant disparity is found in the literature regarding the

Fig. 2. Isotherm experimental data for adsorption of urea onto activated carbon at different temperatures.

adsorption performance of urea onto carbon-based materials. Table 1 summarises the reported urea adsorption capacity values (q_e) for different studies and the respective equilibrium concentrations of urea in solution (C_e). To compare the data, the equivalent q_e for the carbon used in this study at the same C_e is estimated using the isotherms. There are a number of studies about urea adsorption using commercial activated carbons where the authors reported similar adsorption capacity to the one herein achieved (Kameda et al., 2020; Safwat and Matta, 2018). However, other studies have reported adsorption capacities between 10 and 150 times higher for the adsorption of urea using similar commercial (Wernert et al., 2005) and modified (Ganesapillai et al., 2015; Ooi et al., 2017) activated carbons, and it is difficult to postulate the reasons behind such discrepancy in the values. Having said this, the use of these highly adsorbent materials would significantly enhance the urea separation step and improve the performance of the whole process for energy recovery from segregated domestic wastewater.

The isotherm data were fit to the Langmuir (Eq. (2)) and Freundlich (Eq. (3)) equations to elucidate the mechanism of adsorption (Foo and Hameed, 2010). Non-linear fitting was used, so the quality of the fitting was evaluated using the Root Mean Square Error normalised over the range of capacities of each set of experimental data (NRMSE), so they are all comparable (Eq. (4)).

$$q_e = q_m \frac{K_L C_e}{1 + K_L C_e} \quad (2)$$

$$q_e = K_F C_e^{n_F} \quad (3)$$

$$NRMSE = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (q_{exp,i} - q_{cal,i})^2}}{q_{max} - q_{min}} \quad (4)$$

Where q_m (mg g^{-1}) is the monolayer capacity, K_L (L mg^{-1}) and K_F ($\text{mg g}^{-1} (\text{mg L}^{-1})^{n_F}$) are the equilibrium constant of Langmuir and Freundlich Equations respectively, n_F is the heterogeneity factor and n is the number of experimental data. The best-fit parameters are shown in Table 2.

The Langmuir equation assumes that adsorption takes place in a monolayer, while the Freundlich Equation considers that multilayer adsorption can take place (Worch, 2012). Both models fit the experimental data similarly, based on the NRMSE, and therefore, it is difficult to say which one best represents the adsorption process. Similar ambiguity on the best isotherm model to represent the adsorption of urea on activated carbon has been previously reported (Safwat and Matta, 2018). Some studies suggest that the Langmuir model fits better and

Table 1

Comparison of adsorption capacity of urea onto studied activated carbon with literature carbon-based materials.

Material ^a	C_e (mg/L)	Literature q_e (mg/g) ^a	Equivalent q_e for studied carbon at same C_e (mg/g) ^b	Ref.
AC fibre from palm empty fruit bunch	996	877.9	5.8	(Ooi et al., 2017)
Coconut shell-based AC	893	284.0	5.2	(Ganesapillai et al., 2015)
Commercial AC (Chemviron Type F400)	2085	150.6	11.8	(Wernert et al., 2005)
Commercial AC (BAC, Kureha Corp. Japan)	200	1.5	1.2	(Kameda et al., 2020)
Commercial AC (Aquarium Masters, USA)	760	0.8	4.4	(Safwat and Matta, 2018)

^a Temperature ranged from room temperature to 37 °C.

^b Equivalent adsorption capacity of the activated carbon used in this study for the given C_e , calculated using Langmuir parameters obtained at 30 °C.

Table 2

Langmuir and Freundlich Equations fitting parameters for the isotherms of adsorption of urea on activated carbon.

Parameter	30°C	45°C	60°C
Langmuir			
q_m (mg g^{-1})	256.2	285.5	95.4
K_L (L mg^{-1}) $\cdot 10^5$	2.3	1.2	3.9
NRMSE	0.053	0.049	0.143
Freundlich			
K_F ($\text{mg g}^{-1} (\text{mg L}^{-1})^{n_F}$)	0.096	0.023	0.062
n_F	0.67	0.79	0.65
NRMSE	0.068	0.047	0.155

hence monolayer adsorption takes place (Cheng et al., 2018; Ganesapillai et al., 2015), while others suggest that the Freundlich model best represents the process, implying multilayer adsorption (Kameda et al., 2020). The similar fit indicated by both equations may suggest that adsorption is taking place in a monolayer for the range of urea concentrations studied but multilayer adsorption might occur at increasing urea concentration. Higher urea concentrations were not considered in this work as they are not representative of the urea concentration in human urine.

3.2. Adsorption kinetics

Kinetics of adsorption is a key parameter for the design of adsorption systems. Understanding the kinetics of adsorption of urea is crucial for the design of segregated systems so that the production rate of urine is aligned with the adsorption rate of the deployed system. A kinetic study of the adsorption of urea onto the activated carbon was carried out by evaluating the amount of urea adsorbed onto the activated carbon at different times with a starting urea concentration of 20,000 mg/L, in agreement with the urea concentration commonly found in human urine (Simha et al., 2018) (Fig. 3A).

As expected, the amount of adsorbed urea increases with time until reaching equilibrium at a time of 7 min approximately. Adsorption process consists of four consecutive steps: 1. Transport of the solute from the bulk phase of the fluid to the boundary layer around the adsorbent particles; 2. Transport of the solute from the boundary layer to the external surface of the adsorbent, also termed as film diffusion; 3. Transport of the solute from the external surface to the interior of the adsorbent, i.e. intraparticle diffusion; and 4. Adsorption of the solute on the surface of the adsorbent (Worch, 2012). The Boyd Model, a particular solution of the Homogeneous Surface Diffusion Model (Kajjumba et al., 2018), can be used to determine the limiting step. The model is described by the following equations (Eq. (5) - Eq. (9)):

$$F = 1 - \frac{6}{\pi^2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} \exp(-n^2 B_t) \quad (5)$$

$$F = \frac{q_t}{q_e} \quad (6)$$

$$B_t = \frac{D_i \pi^2 t}{R^2} \quad (7)$$

Where F is the fraction of the solute adsorbed at a time t to the solute adsorbed at equilibrium (Eq. (5)). B_t is a function of time which is influenced by the effective diffusion coefficient D_i and the radius of the adsorbent particles R , as expressed in Eq. (7). The value of B_t can be calculated as follows (Kajjumba et al., 2018):

$$0 \leq F \leq 0.85 \rightarrow B_t = 2\pi - \frac{\pi^2 F}{3} - 2\pi \left(1 - \frac{\pi F}{3}\right)^{1/2} \quad (8)$$

$$0 \leq F \leq 0.85 \rightarrow B_t = -0.4977 - \ln(1 - F) \quad (9)$$

As it can be observed from Fig. 3B, the kinetic data fit the model with

Fig. 3. Kinetic study of the adsorption of urea onto activated carbon. $C_0 = 20,000$ mg/L; Adsorbent dosage = 40 g/L; $T = 30$ °C. A: Time-evolution of adsorbed urea. B: Fitting of the kinetic data to Boyd Model.

an R^2 of 0.95 and an intercept close to zero which, according to the Boyd Model, means that the intraparticle diffusion is the limiting step (Kaj-jumba et al., 2018).

Using Eq. (7) and assuming that the granules can be approximated to spherical particles of 0.8 mm the effective diffusion coefficient can be calculated, obtaining a value of $7.78 \cdot 10^{-11}$ m²/s. This value is on the higher side of the typical range of the diffusion coefficient values for activated carbon for organic compounds (from 10^{-11} m²/s for small molecules to 10^{-15} m²/s for big molecules) (Worch, 2012). Urea is a small molecule, so it diffuses into the pores of the activated carbon faster than most organic compounds, which are normally much bigger and therefore present a higher mass transfer resistance.

3.3. Step 2. Desorption and decomposition of urea

Once urea is collected from the aqueous solution by adsorption on activated carbon, the adsorbent needs to be regenerated for its reuse and urea release. Regeneration of activated carbon was carried out thermally at 250 °C to combine the activated carbon regeneration with the urea decomposition, normally taking place at $\sim 130 - 200$ °C, producing ammonia and carbon dioxide.

Temperature programmed desorption (TPD) of the saturated activated carbon was carried out to evaluate the production of ammonia (NH₃), isocyanic acid (HNCO) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) resulted from thermal decomposition of urea. The concentration profiles of the outlet gases monitored during TPD are shown in Fig. 4A.

Solid urea (NH₂CONH₂) thermally decomposes into ammonia and

isocyanic acid according to reaction R. 1, starting at 133 °C. The isocyanic acid can then undergo hydrolysis to further convert it into NH₃ and CO₂ following R. 2 (Koebel and Strutz, 2003).

It can be observed that the production of NH₃ occurs between 140 – 190 °C. This matches with the temperature of solid urea decomposition (Koebel and Strutz, 2003), which points that NH₃ is being produced through decomposition of the adsorbed urea as NH₃ and HNCO. No HNCO is observed in the same range of temperatures. This may suggest that most of the HNCO is hydrolysed following R. 2 with interstitial water present in the activated carbon after its drying at 80 °C.

A rise in the amount of CO₂ produced is observed for the saturated activated carbon compared to the fresh one in Fig. 4B, which is additional evidence of the HNCO hydrolysis, as the difference in the carbon dioxide resulted from this reaction. Other materials such as Fe/ZSM-5 and TiO₂ (Lundström et al., 2011; Piazzesi et al., 2006) have been identified to catalyse the hydrolysis of HNCO, so it is possible that the activated carbon has a similar catalytic role despite not having been previously reported in the literature. It is also observed that fresh activated carbon releases CO₂ which is associated to the desorption of various oxygen functional groups present on its surface (Figueiredo et al., 1999). As expected, no formation of NH₃ or HNCO was observed on the TPD of the fresh activated carbon.

In Fig. 4A, a small peak of HNCO appears between 250 – 275 °C.

Fig. 4. A: Outlet gases concentration as a function of temperature during the thermal treatment of urea adsorbed on activated carbon. B: Carbon dioxide concentration as a function of temperature during thermal treatment of fresh and saturated activated carbon. Temperature change rate = 10 K/min; Ar flowrate = 50 mL/min; AC mass = 50 mg; adsorbed urea (for saturated AC) = 58 mg/g.

Apart from hydrolysis, isocyanic acid can also undergo other reactions that form by-products such as biuret ($C_2H_5N_3O_2$) and subsequently cyanuric acid ($C_3H_3N_3O_3$). At higher temperatures (200 - 300 °C) some of these compounds can decompose leading to the production of HNCO. Indeed, Schaber et al. (2004) found that cyanuric acid decomposes between 250 – 275 °C into HNCO, following R. 3 (Schaber et al., 2004), which perfectly matches with the HNCO profile found herein.

Therefore, the following mechanism is proposed for the decomposition of the urea adsorbed on activated carbon. Firstly, adsorbed urea is thermally decomposed between 140 – 190 °C into NH_3 and HNCO which are desorbed from the surface of the carbon into gas phase. Most of the HNCO undergoes hydrolysis with interstitial water trapped inside the carbon to produce more NH_3 and CO_2 . However, a fraction of the HNCO undergo side reactions that lead to the formation of other compounds such as biuret and cyanuric acid. The latter decomposes between 250 and 275 °C producing HNCO.

3.4. Regeneration of activated carbon

To evaluate the efficiency of the regeneration of the activated carbon, several adsorption/desorption cycles were carried out. For this, after thermal treatment of the saturated carbon at 250 °C, a new adsorption cycle was carried out. The adsorption capacities of carbons during 5 consecutive adsorption/desorption cycles are shown in Fig. 5.

The fresh activated carbon used in cycle 1 reached a urea adsorption capacity of 63 mg/g, while the capacities observed for the regenerated carbons from cycles 2 to 5 ranged from 59 to 68 mg/g. These values are not statistically different and hence, it can be considered that the adsorption capacity remains constant during at least 5 adsorption/desorption cycles, suggesting that urea is completely desorbed and decomposed in the form of ammonia and isocyanic acid (R. 1). The constant capacity of the regenerated carbon during several cycles means that in a real-scale application of the process, the adsorbent can be recycled multiple times, enhancing the operability and sustainability of the process, and decreasing costs.

3.5. Step 3. Catalytic decomposition of ammonia into hydrogen

Thermal desorption and decomposition of urea in step 2 was coupled with in-situ catalytic decomposition of ammonia using a ruthenium supported on carbon nanotubes catalyst in step 3. A bed of saturated

Fig. 5. Adsorption capacity of urea with regenerated carbon after five consecutive adsorption/desorption cycles. Adsorption: $C_0 = 20,000$ mg/L; Adsorbent dosage = 40 g/L; $T = 30$ °C. Regeneration: N_2 flow = 20 mL/min; $T = 250$ °C; $t = 210$ min.

activated carbon was placed inside a first reactor connected in series with a second reactor containing Ru/CNT as catalyst for ammonia decomposition (see Fig. 6 for schematic). The first reactor was kept at 200 °C to trigger the desorption of urea and decomposition into ammonia according to the TPD data abovementioned. The temperature of the second reactor was kept at 400 °C to ensure high levels of ammonia decomposition conversion (Hill and Torrente-Murciano, 2014). Fig. 6 shows the time-evolution of hydrogen and ammonia concentration in the outlet gas after the second and the first reactor respectively.

Thermal decomposition of urea achieved in step 2 produced ammonia which was subsequently used to obtain hydrogen following its catalytic decomposition (R. 4) (Hill and Torrente-Murciano, 2015).

As it can be observed in Fig. 6, under the studied experimental conditions, a stable concentration of hydrogen was produced at the outlet of the second reactor, demonstrating the feasibility of the process to produce hydrogen from urea in solution. After an arbitrary period (10 min), the second reactor was by-passed to measure the outlet of the first reactor. As shown in the shadowed area of the graph in Fig. 6, only ammonia is detected with no hydrogen present. These results confirm that hydrogen at the outlet of the second reactor is indeed a product of ammonia decomposition (and no residual hydrogen from the pre-treatment step for reduction of the catalyst).

These results demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed process: adsorption of urea onto activated carbon and its subsequent desorption and decomposition into hydrogen. The hydrogen can then be used for energy production in a fuel cell, with an additional purification step. These findings open the door to new treatment models of domestic wastewater, as urine could be collected and used to produce hydrogen due to its high concentration of urea.

3.6. Preliminary energy balance feasibility calculations

Preliminary energy balance calculations were carried out to determine the feasibility of the process in terms of energy recovery. This analysis uses recent insights about the operating parameters reported for the municipal wastewater treatment plant in Lleida, Spain (Palatsi et al., 2021). The estimation of hydrogen production and energy recovery in Lleida considers the collection of urea from segregated domestic wastewater in the whole city (160,000 inhabitants). Every person was assumed to daily produce 1.5 L of urine with an average urea concentration of 20,000 mg/L, resulting in 4800 kg_{urea}/day. The removal of urea by adsorption onto activated carbon was 100%.

The approximated efficiencies for the steps involved in the process are summarised in Table 3. The efficiency of the thermal decomposition of urea into ammonia and isocyanic acid, and the hydrolysis of the isocyanic acid are estimated to be 100% and 80% based on the results obtained herein for the decomposition of urea into ammonia. Ammonia decomposition into hydrogen reaches 100% conversion if the temperature and residence time are high enough in the presence of a catalyst. Thus, conversions of 100% have been reported at 380 °C (Hill and Torrente-Murciano, 2015). The efficiency of hydrogen to heat was assumed to be the same than that achieved in conventional boilers (90%) (U.S. Department of Energy, 2021). For electricity production, the hydrogen is to be used in a proton-exchange membrane (PEM) fuel cell (commercially available), where its conversion to electricity presents a 48% efficiency (Taner, 2018).

Considering reactions R. 1, R. 2 and R. 4, and the values of efficiency summarised in Table 3, a hydrogen production of 432 kg/day would be expected. The energy contained in this amount of hydrogen can be estimated as 14,225 kWh/day using the lower heating value of hydrogen (119 MJ/kg).

However, there is a series of energy requirements associated with

Fig. 6. Hydrogen and ammonia production from thermal treatment and catalytic treatment of urea adsorbed on activated carbon. He flow = 4 mL/min; AC mass = 4.5 g; adsorbed urea = 58 mg/g; AC $T = 200^{\circ}\text{C}$; cat mass = 60 mg; cat $T = 400^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Table 3

Efficiencies assumed for the preliminary energy balance calculation of the designed process.

Step	Efficiency (%)	Ref.
Urea decomposition into NH_3 and HNCO	100	This work
HNCO hydrolysis	80	This work
NH_3 decomposition into H_2	100	(Hill and Torrente-Murciano, 2015)
Hydrogen to heat	90	(U.S. Department of Energy, 2021)
Hydrogen to electricity	48	(Taner, 2018)

this hydrogen production. Step 1 of the process, the adsorption of urea does not require any energy if a static system (e.g., driven by gravity) is designed. For the desorption of urea and production of ammonia (step 2), the activated carbon needs to be heated up to 200°C . The amount of activated carbon required to adsorb urea can be estimated by the adsorption capacity. While in batch experiments the adsorption capacity is in equilibrium with the final concentration of the urea in solution, in a fixed bed adsorber the adsorption capacity is in equilibrium with the initial concentration of urea. This capacity was estimated using the Langmuir parameters at 30°C from Table 2 and an equilibrium concentration of 20,000 mg/L of urea, obtaining a value of 81 mg/g. Then, given the amount of urea to be absorbed daily ($4800 \text{ kg}_{\text{urea}}/\text{day}$) a total adsorbent mass of 59 t of activated carbon would be required. One should note that this amount of activated carbon would be distributed in the different buildings of the city and regenerated periodically (e.g. daily). Considering the specific heat capacity of activated carbon, 0.844 kJ/kg K (Uddin et al., 2018), the energy required for heating the carbon was estimated as 2362 kWh/day. Additionally, the adsorbed urea also has to be heated up, and the necessary energy was estimated assuming that the specific heat of adsorbed urea is the same as the one for solid urea, 1.5 kJ/kg K (Tischer et al., 2019). Therefore, for increasing the temperature of urea from 30°C to 200°C the heat required would be 351 kWh/day, much lower than the contribution of the activated carbon. Similarly, water is required for the hydrolysis of HNCO. It was considered that the water trapped inside the carbon can drive the hydrolysis. The water trapped in the carbon was considered to be liquid, so the needed heat for increasing the temperature from liquid water at 30°C to water vapour at 200°C amounts to 884 kWh/day. This value is much higher than the heating requirements for urea as water has a considerably high latent heat of vaporisation. Furthermore, the enthalpy

of reaction of urea decomposition and HNCO hydrolysis reactions are 185.5 kJ/mol_{urea} and $-95.9 \text{ kJ/mol}_{\text{HNCO}}$, respectively (Koebel and Strutz, 2003; Tischer et al., 2019) which results in a net heating requirement of 2288 kWh/day for both reactions. As a result, the total energy required for step 2, considering the regeneration of the activated carbon and production of ammonia amounts to 5884 kWh/day.

The hydrogen production step (step 3) requires the heat associated with heating the ammonia to an appropriate decomposition temperature and the enthalpy of the reaction. From step 2, the produced ammonia and carbon dioxide need to be further heated up from 200 to 400°C . Considering the ammonia gaseous specific heat of 2.2 kJ/kg K (Tischer et al., 2019) and the carbon dioxide specific heat of 0.85 kJ/kg K (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2021), the energy required was estimated at 438 kWh/day. Ammonia decomposition is an endothermic reaction with an enthalpy of 92 kJ/mol_{NH₃} (Tischer et al., 2019), which leads to an additional heating requirement of 1846 kWh/day. Therefore, the energy input required for the ammonia decomposition step is 2284 kWh/day, less than half of that required for production of ammonia. The total energy demand of the system would

Fig. 7. Distribution of energy requirements to produce hydrogen from urea present in human urine.

then be 8169 kWh/day, which is approximately half of the energy contained in the recovered H_2 . Fig. 7 summarises all the energetic requirements for the production of hydrogen from waste urea.

The hydrogen could be used to cover heat demands abovementioned, achieving a self-sustained energy process. Considering a 90% efficiency, the remaining energy stored as hydrogen and available for electricity production would be then 5151 kWh/day. Using the hydrogen in a PEM fuel cell, with 48% efficiency (Taner, 2018), the net electrical production of the studied process would be 2472 kWh/day.

In addition to a net electrical production, the removal of urea from wastewater simultaneously decreases the energy requirements associated to the removal of nitrogen at WWTP. The WWTP of Lleida treats an average wastewater flow of 55,241 m^3 /day with an average energy consumption of 0.24 kWh/ m^3 . This leads to a total consumption of 13,181 kWh/day, from which nitrogen removal represents more than 48% (Palatsi et al., 2021). Assuming that around 80% percent of the nitrogen in a WWTP comes from urine (Maurer et al., 2003), and that around 90% of that nitrogen is present in the form of urea (Simha et al., 2018), savings of 4575 kWh/day could be achieved in this WWTP, which represents around 35% of the electricity consumption of the whole plant. Both, the net electrical production and the savings in the WWTP together counts 7048 kWh/day. A summary of the energy analysis results is shown in Fig. 8 and detailed calculations for the energy analysis can be found in the Supplementary Information.

If these values are normalised by the volume of treated urine, a hydrogen production of 1.8 kg- H_2 / m^3 urine with an electricity production of 10.3 kWh/ m^3 urine would be achieved. Considering the savings at WWTP, the total net energy balance amounts to 29.4 kWh/ m^3 of treated urine.

Some of the operation conditions can be improved to enhance the energy efficiency of the process. In this regard, an increase in the adsorption capacity and a decrease in the ammonia decomposition temperature would lead to the bigger benefits to decrease the heating energy requirements. A sensitivity analysis was carried out to evaluate the effect of these two parameters on the balance of the energy recovery system (Fig. 9). The adsorption capacity was evaluated in a range from 81 mg/g, which is the capacity of the activated carbon used in this work, to 880 mg/g, which is the highest urea adsorption capacity reported in the literature for a carbon-based adsorbent (Ooi et al., 2017). The ammonia decomposition temperature was evaluated ranging from 200 °C, (temperature at which the activated carbon is regenerated and ammonia produced by urea decomposition), and 400 °C (temperature considered for hydrogen production from ammonia).

Fig. 8. Summary of the energy analysis for the installation of the process in the city of Lleida, Spain.

Fig. 9. Sensitivity analysis of the effect of urea adsorption capacity and ammonia decomposition temperature on the net energy production of the designed process.

Fig. 9 shows that foreseen improvements in the urea adsorption capacity of carbons has a greater impact on the energy balance than the ammonia decomposition temperature. An increase in adsorption capacity from 81 to 880 mg/g, as previously reported in the literature (Ooi et al., 2017) would reduce the amount of carbon required from 59 to 5 tons/day and hence the associated energy required for carbon heating would decrease from 2362 to 217 kWh/day, making the whole step 2 (regeneration of the adsorbent) energy demand to decrease by \sim 40% (from 5884 to 3740 kWh/day). The effect of increasing the adsorption capacity on the regeneration energy requirement is particularly relevant up to a capacity of \sim 300 mg/g (step 2 energy demand = 4160 kWh/day). This reduction comes from the use of much less carbon and hence, less heating being required to increase the temperature up to 200 °C. Further increases in the carbon adsorption capacity does not have such a substantial effect as the rest of the heating requirements of step 2 (3523 kWh/day), which are constant independently of the adsorption capacity, starts to be predominant relative to the heating for increasing carbon temperature during regeneration. Furthermore, an increase in the adsorption capacity would have a very large effect on the capital costs of the process, as much less volume of activated carbon would be required and then the dimensions of the adsorption columns would be minimized.

In addition, a decrease in the ammonia decomposition temperature can improve the overall efficiency of the system, but in a much more limited way. The decrease of the operation temperature would reduce the needs for heating up the ammonia and carbon dioxide, but in the original scenario these contributions only accounted for \sim 5% of the total energy demand, so even if completely removed (working at 200 °C), the effect is not as relevant as increasing the adsorption capacity.

Based on this sensitivity analysis and considering the current developments of activated carbon, the net energy production from human urine could be increased. A new scenario (optimistic future scenario) was analysed considering the use of reported activated carbon treated with microwave irradiation with an adsorption capacity of 330 mg/g (Ganesapillai et al., 2015). In addition, another scenario (conservative future scenario) has been considered taking into consideration the energy penalty associated to the evaporation of water during the drying process of the activated carbon. For this, the amount of water to wet the activated carbon was experimentally determined to be 350 mg/g by weighing the carbon before and after adsorption experiments without urea in the solution. A summary and comparison of the baseline (this work) and the future conservative and optimistic scenarios are shown in

Table 4
Summary of the energy analysis of the baseline and future scenarios analysed.

	Baseline Scenario	Conservative future Scenario	Optimistic future Scenario
Hydrogen production (kg/day)	430	430	430
Energy stored in H ₂ (kWh/day)	14,225	14,225	14,225
Energy consumption (kWh/day)	8170	9413	6385
Net electrical production (kWh/day)	2470	1810	3425
Electricity savings in WWTP (kWh/day)	4575	4575	4575
Net balance (kWh/day) ^a	7050	6385	8000

^a Sum of net electrical production from H₂ and electricity savings in WWTP.

Table 4. The latter two scenarios represent 100% and 0% adsorbed water in the activated carbon while the real scenario is likely to be within these limits as some water will naturally evaporate during the process

The deployment of state-of-the-art activated carbons can enhance the net electricity production of the process by ~40%, as can be observed comparing the optimistic and the baseline scenario, highlighting the importance on the development of more efficient materials for the adsorption of urea. The full thermal-evaporation of the adsorbed water, even when using highly adsorptive carbons, can increase the energy requirements of the process almost 50%, however as mentioned before the real scenario would likely be within the optimistic and the conservative ones. The adsorbed water is highly dependant to the amount of carbon required for the removal of urea and hence to the adsorption capacity stressing even more the importance of having efficient materials for the adsorption of urea.

3.7. Future developments and outlook

Energy recovery from the urea present in human urine has been demonstrated as a proof-of-concept using model solutions of urea with a similar concentration found in human urine (20,000 mg/L). The selectivity of the adsorption towards urea when found in real human urine samples must be studied to evaluate if it has a detrimental effect on the process. Furthermore, the effect of the adsorption of other components during the desorption and regeneration step has to be further evaluated to check whether the regeneration efficiency found here is maintained.

These promising preliminary results show that HNCO resulted from thermal urea decomposition does not completely hydrolyse, but partially decomposes into by-products. The effect of these compounds on the efficiency of the system needs to be further investigated as they are likely to cause problems over time during the ammonia decomposition step by poisoning and/or degrading the catalyst. Similarly, other components present in the urine can also interact with both the adsorbent by decreasing its capacity and/or the catalysts by poisoning. To avoid the latter, an intermediate step for purification of the ammonia may be required.

The catalyst herein used for production of hydrogen is ruthenium-based. However, ruthenium is a scarce and expensive metal, so considerable effort is being made to design catalysts from cost-competitive readily available materials to make the process viable at large-scale by substituting ruthenium with non-noble metals (Bell and Torrente-Murciano, 2016) or bi-metallic alloys (Kirste et al., 2021, 2020).

The process is thought to use the produced hydrogen in fuel cells for electricity generation. If using a proton-membrane exchange (PEM) fuel cell, a separation step is needed to purify hydrogen to avoid poisoning the fuel cell catalysts by any ammonia impurities (Lan and Tao, 2014). A membrane reactor is an attractive option with the separation of

hydrogen, particularly at low temperatures to drive an equilibrium shift in favour of ammonia decomposition. Advanced reactor designs and process integration will also be required to ensure full ammonia utilisation even at equilibrium-limited low temperature conditions. An attractive alternative is solid oxide fuel cells (SOFC) which have similar efficiencies to PEM fuel cells and have the advantage of being more robust to fuel impurities, including recent development of direct ammonia SOFC fuel cells. However, due to the high operating temperature they normally suffer from long start-up times and are sensitive to shutdowns (Malik et al., 2021; Rathore et al., 2021).

4. Conclusions

In this paper, we demonstrate the feasibility of a new process for the conversion of waste urea in human urine into an energy source. In this way, decentralised wastewater systems present an efficient alternative to the conventional centralised plants where the current biological removal of nitrogen compounds represent a high fraction (> 50%) of their energy demand. The concept is demonstrated in this study by adsorption of urea (at the production point) using activated carbon. Its consecutive thermal regeneration not only desorbs the urea but also leads to its decomposition into ammonia and isocyanic acid, the latter being partially hydrolysed into more ammonia and carbon dioxide. Such regeneration process preserves the adsorption capacity of the activated carbon for at least 5 cycles. This regeneration step is successfully coupled to ammonia decomposition catalyst to produce hydrogen. Preliminary energy balance calculations show that the urea adsorption capacity of the selected activated carbon plays a key role on the feasibility of the process. As illustration, with the adoption of this process in a city with 160,000 inhabitants, 430 kg/day of hydrogen could be obtained to achieve a net electricity production of 2500 kWh/day. In addition, it would reduce the energy requirements at the wastewater treatment plant by 4600 kWh/day, a 35% of the total energy demand. As a result, this work demonstrates the proof-of-concept for the utilisation of urea in human urine as an energy resource in segregated systems.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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References

- Baeyens, J., Zhang, H., Nie, J., Appels, L., Dewil, R., Ansart, R., Deng, Y., 2020. Reviewing the potential of bio-hydrogen production by fermentation. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 131, 110023 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.110023>.
- Bell, T.E., Torrente-Murciano, L., 2016. H₂ production via ammonia decomposition using non-noble metal catalysts: a review. *Top. Catal.* 59, 1438–1457. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11244-016-0653-4>.
- Bell, T.E., Zhan, G., Wu, K., Zeng, C.H., Torrente-Murciano, L., 2017. Modification of Ammonia Decomposition Activity of Ruthenium Nanoparticles by N-Doping of CNT Supports 60, 1251–1259. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11244-017-0806-0>.
- Bernhard, A.M., Peitz, D., Elsener, M., Wokaun, A., Kröcher, O., 2012. Hydrolysis and thermolysis of urea and its decomposition byproducts biuret, cyanuric acid and melamine over anatase TiO₂. *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2011.12.013>.

- Cheah, W.K., Sim, Y.L., Yeoh, F.Y., 2016. Amine-functionalized mesoporous silica for urea adsorption. *Mater. Chem. Phys.* 175, 151–157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2016.03.007>.
- Cheng, Y.C., Fu, C.C., Hsiao, Y.S., Chien, C.C., Juang, R.S., 2018. Clearance of low molecular-weight uremic toxins p-cresol, creatinine, and urea from simulated serum by adsorption. *J. Mol. Liq.* 252, 203–210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2017.12.084>.
- Deng, Y., Dewil, R., Appels, L., Van Tulden, F., Li, S., Yang, M., Baeyens, J., 2022. Hydrogen-enriched natural gas in a decarbonization perspective. *Fuel* 318, 123680. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2022.123680>.
- Egle, L., Rechberger, H., Zessner, M., 2015. Overview and description of technologies for recovering phosphorus from municipal wastewater. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 105, 325–346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2015.09.016>.
- Estévez, S., Feijoo, G., Moreira, M.T., 2022. Environmental synergies in decentralized wastewater treatment at a hotel resort. *J. Environ. Manage.* 317, 115392. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.115392>.
- Figueredo, J.L., Pereira, M.F.R., Freitas, M.M.A., Ôrfão, J.J.M., 1999. Modification of the surface chemistry of activated carbons. *Carbon N. Y.* 37, 1379–1389. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0008-6223\(98\)00333-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0008-6223(98)00333-9).
- Foo, K.Y., Hameed, B.H., 2010. Insights into the modeling of adsorption isotherm systems. *Chem. Eng. J.* 156, 2–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2009.09.013>.
- Ganesapillai, M., Simha, P., Zabanitout, A., 2015. Closed-loop fertility cycle: realizing sustainability in sanitation and agricultural production through the design and implementation of nutrient recovery systems for human urine. *Sustain. Prod. Consum.* 4, 36–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2015.08.004>.
- Hill, A.K., Torrente-Murciano, L., 2015. Low temperature H₂ production from ammonia using ruthenium-based catalysts: synergetic effect of promoter and support. *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2015.02.011>.
- Hill, A.K., Torrente-Murciano, L., 2014. In-situ H₂ production via low temperature decomposition of ammonia: insights into the role of cesium as a promoter. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2014.03.043>.
- Hu, Z., Mahin, J., Datta, S., Bell, T.E., Torrente-Murciano, L., 2019a. Ru-Based Catalysts for H₂ Production from Ammonia: effect of 1D Support Top Catal. 62, 1169–1177. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11244-018-1058-3>.
- Hu, Z., Mahin, J., Torrente-Murciano, L., 2019b. A MOF-templated approach for designing ruthenium-cesium catalysts for hydrogen generation from ammonia. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 44, 30108–30118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJHYDENE.2019.09.174>.
- Kajjumba, G.W., Emik, S., Öngen, A., Özcan, H.K., Aydin, S., 2018. Modelling of Adsorption Kinetic Processes—Errors, Theory and Application. In: Edebalı, S. (Ed.), *Advanced Sorption Process Applications*. IntechOpen, London. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.80495>.
- Kameda, T., Horikoshi, K., Kumagai, S., Saito, Y., Yoshioka, T., 2020. Adsorption of urea, creatinine, and uric acid onto spherical activated carbon. *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 237, 116367. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2019.116367>.
- Kirste, K.G., Laassiri, S., Hu, Z., Stoian, D., Torrente-Murciano, L., Hargreaves, J.S.J., Mathisen, K., 2020. XAS investigation of silica aerogel supported cobalt rhenium catalysts for ammonia decomposition. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 22, 18932–18949. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d0cp00558d>.
- Kirste, K.G., McAulay, K., Bell, T.E., Stoian, D., Laassiri, S., Daisley, A., Hargreaves, J.S.J., Mathisen, K., Torrente-Murciano, L., 2021. CO_x-free hydrogen production from ammonia – mimicking the activity of Ru catalysts with unsupported Co-Re alloys. *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* 280, 119405. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2020.119405>.
- Koebel, M., Strutz, E.O., 2003. Thermal and hydrolytic decomposition of urea for automotive selective catalytic reduction systems: thermochemical and practical aspects. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 42, 2093–2100. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie020950o>.
- Kuntke, P., Sleutels, T.H.J.A., Saakes, M., Buisman, C.J.N., 2014. Hydrogen production and ammonium recovery from urine by a Microbial Electrolysis Cell. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 39, 4771–4778. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2013.10.089>.
- Kuntke, P., Śmiech, K.M., Bruning, H., Zeeman, G., Saakes, M., Sleutels, T.H.J.A., Hamelers, H.V.M., Buisman, C.J.N., 2012. Ammonium recovery and energy production from urine by a microbial fuel cell. *Water Res* 46, 2627–2636. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2012.02.025>.
- Lan, R., Tao, S., 2014. Ammonia as a suitable fuel for fuel cells. *Front. Energy Res.* 2, 3–6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feng.2014.00035>.
- Lehmann, H.D., Marten, R., Gullberg, C.A., 1981. How to catch urea? Considerations on urea removal from hemofiltrate. *Artif. Organs* 5, 278–285. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1525-1594.1981.tb04002.x>.
- Li, S., Kang, Q., Baeyens, J., Zhang, H.L., Deng, Y.M., 2020. Hydrogen production: state of technology. *IOP Conf. Ser. Earth Environ. Sci.* 544, 012011. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/544/1/012011>.
- Li, S., Zhang, H., Nie, J., Dewil, R., Baeyens, J., Deng, Y., 2021. The direct reduction of iron ore with hydrogen. *Sustainability* 13, 8866. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13168866>.
- Lundström, A., Snelling, T., Morsing, P., Gabriellson, P., Senar, E., Olsson, L., 2011. Urea decomposition and H₂CO hydrolysis studied over titanium dioxide, Fe-Beta and γ -Alumina. *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* 106, 273–279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2011.05.010>.
- Malik, V., Srivastava, S., Bhatnagar, M.K., Vishnoi, M., 2021. Comparative study and analysis between solid oxide fuel cells (SOFC) and proton exchange membrane (PEM) fuel cell – a review. *Mater. Today Proc.* 47, 2270–2275. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MATPR.2021.04.203>.
- Maurer, M., Schwegler, P., Larsen, T.A., 2003. Nutrients in urine: energetic aspects of removal and recovery. *Water Sci. Technol.* 48, 37–46. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2003.0011>.
- National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2021. Carbon dioxide - the NIST WebBook [WWW Document]. Available from: <https://webbook.nist.gov/cgi/cbook.cgi?ID=124-38-9> (accessed 8.6.21).
- Ooi, C.H., Cheah, W.K., Sim, Y.L., Pung, S.Y., Yeoh, F.Y., 2017. Conversion and characterization of activated carbon fiber derived from palm empty fruit bunch waste and its kinetic study on urea adsorption. *J. Environ. Manage.* 197, 199–205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.03.083>.
- Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries, 2017. *World Oil Outlook 2040*. ISBN: 978-3-9503936-4-4. Available from: <http://www.opec.org>.
- Palatsi, J., Ripoll, F., Benzal, A., Pijuan, M., Romero-güiza, M.S., 2021. Enhancement of biological nutrient removal process with advanced process control tools in full-scale wastewater treatment plant. *Water Res* 200, 117212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2021.117212>.
- Piazzesi, G., Devadas, M., Kröcher, O., Elsener, M., Wokaun, A., 2006. Isocyanic acid hydrolysis over Fe-ZSM5 in urea-SCR. *Catal. Commun.* 7, 600–603. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catcom.2006.01.022>.
- Rahimpour, M.R., 2004. A non-ideal rate-based model for industrial urea thermal hydrolyser. *Chem. Eng. Process. Process Intensif.* 43, 1299–1307. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccep.2003.12.005>.
- Rathore, S.S., Biswas, S., Fini, D., Kulkarni, A.P., Giddey, S., 2021. Direct ammonia solid-oxide fuel cells: a review of progress and prospects. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 46, 35365–35384. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJHYDENE.2021.08.092>.
- Rossi, L., Lienert, J., Larsen, T.A., 2009. Real-life efficiency of urine source separation. *J. Environ. Manage.* 90, 1909–1917. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2009.01.006>.
- Safwat, S.M., Matta, M.E., 2018. Adsorption of urea onto granular activated alumina: a comparative study with granular activated carbon. *J. Dispers. Sci. Technol.* 39, 1699–1709. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01932691.2018.1461644>.
- Saleem, J., Shahid, U.Bin, Hijab, M., Mackey, H., McKay, G., 2019. Production and applications of activated carbons as adsorbents from olive stones. *Biomass Convers. Biorefinery* 9, 775–802. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13399-019-00473-7>.
- Schaber, P.M., Colson, J., Higgins, S., Thielen, D., Anspach, B., Brauer, J., 2004. Thermal decomposition (pyrolysis) of urea in an open reaction vessel. *Thermochim. Acta* 424, 131–142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TCA.2004.05.018>.
- Simha, P., Zabanitout, A., Ganesapillai, M., 2018. Continuous urea-nitrogen recycling from human urine: a step towards creating a human excreta based bio-economy. *J. Clean. Prod.* 172, 4152–4161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.01.062>.
- Smith, C., Hill, A.K., Torrente-Murciano, L., 2020. Current and future role of Haber-Bosch ammonia in a carbon-free energy landscape. *Energy Environ. Sci.* 13, 331. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9ee02873k>.
- Stillwell, A.S., Hoppock, D.C., Webber, M.E., 2010. Energy recovery from wastewater treatment plants in the United States: a case study of the energy-water nexus. *Sustainability* 2, 945–962. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su2040945>.
- Taner, T., 2018. Energy and exergy analyze of PEM fuel cell: a case study of modeling and simulations. *Energy* 143, 284–294. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.10.102>.
- Tao, W., Bayraktar, A., Wang, Y., Agyeman, F., 2019. Three-stage treatment for nitrogen and phosphorus recovery from human urine: hydrolysis, precipitation and vacuum stripping. *J. Environ. Manage.* 249, 109435. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.109435>.
- Tischer, S., Börnhorst, M., Amsler, J., Schoch, G., Deutschmann, O., 2019. Thermodynamics and reaction mechanism of urea decomposition. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 21, 16785–16797. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9cp01529a>.
- UNESCO, 2019. *The United Nations World Water Development Report 2019: Leaving No One Behind*. Paris, UNESCO. ISBN: 978-92-3-100309-7. Available from: <https://en.unesco.org/themes/water-security/wrap/wwrdr/2019>.
- Uddin, K., Islam, Amirul, M., Mitra, S., Lee, boong, J., Thu, K., Saha, B.B., Koyama, S., 2018. Specific heat capacities of carbon-based adsorbents for adsorption heat pump application. *Appl. Therm. Eng.* 129, 117–126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2017.09.057>.
- U.S. Department of Energy, 2021. *Furnaces and Boilers* [WWW Document]. Available from: <https://www.energy.gov/energysaver/home-heating-systems/furnaces-and-boilers> (accessed 8.5.21).
- Von Münch, E., Winker, M., 2011. *Technology review of urine diversion components*. Detusche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) GmbH.
- Wernert, P., Schäfer, O., Ghobarkar, H., Denoyel, R., 2005. Adsorption properties of zeolites for artificial kidney applications. *Microporous Mesoporous Mater* 83, 101–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2005.03.018>.
- Wilson, L.D., Xue, C., 2013. Macromolecular sorbent materials for urea capture. *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 128, 667–675. <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.38247>.
- Worch, E., 2012. Adsorption Technology in Water Treatment: fundamentals, Processes and Modeling. De Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110240238>.
- Xue, C., Wilson, L.D., 2016. Kinetic study on urea uptake with chitosan based sorbent materials. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 135, 180–186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2015.08.090>.
- Zamora, P., Georgieva, T., Salcedo, I., Elzinga, N., Kuntke, P., Buisman, C.J.N., 2017a. Long-term operation of a pilot-scale reactor for phosphorus recovery as struvite from source-separated urine. *J. Chem. Technol. Biotechnol.* 92, 1035–1045. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jctb.5079>.
- Zamora, P., Georgieva, T., Ter Heijne, A., Sleutels, T.H.J.A., Jeremiasse, A.W., Saakes, M., Buisman, C.J.N., Kuntke, P., 2017b. Ammonia recovery from urine in a scaled-up Microbial Electrolysis Cell. *J. Power Sources* 356, 491–499. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2017.02.089>.